

23 **Abstract**

24 The parameters to extract polysaccharide-enriched fractions (PEF) from mushrooms
25 using MAE (microwave-assisted extraction) were adjusted following a full factorial 3^2
26 experimental design. The highest yield and total carbohydrate values, using *Lentinula edodes* as
27 model mushroom, were obtained at 180 °C and 30 min. Several mushroom species were submitted
28 to MAE and their PEF yields ranged between 12.1-44.2%. (1→3)- β -Glucans determination using
29 a conventional fluorimetric method changed depending on the standard utilized. NMR analyses
30 of PEF indicated that the presence of other polysaccharides in the extracts or their specific folding,
31 might impair the proper determination of (1→3) linkages by the fluorophore. Mushrooms from
32 Cantharellales order contained (1→3)- β -glucans but they were not detected with the fluorimetric
33 method. Therefore, although the method (after adjustments) was sensitive enough to detect their
34 presence in many mushroom extracts, it cannot be used for all species and it is also not
35 recommended for quantitative determinations.

36 1. Introduction

37 Mushroom polysaccharides showed many beneficial properties for human health. They were
38 described as immunomodulatory, antibacterial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory,
39 hypocholesterolemic agents etc. (Roncero-Ramos & Delgado-Andrade, 2017). Although
40 mushrooms can synthesize a wide variety of polysaccharides, β -D-glucans are those pointed as
41 responsible for most of the biological activities.

42 β -D-Glucans are present in all mushroom species since they are the major constituents of
43 fungal cell walls contributing to their structure (Ruthes, Smiderle, & Iacomini, 2015). Although
44 linear β -D-glucans were also isolated from certain species, their molecular structures mainly
45 contain a (1 \rightarrow 3)-linked backbone chain with substitutions at O-6 by single units of β -D-
46 glucopyranose (Ruthes et al., 2015). Previous studies suggested that the biological properties of
47 these compounds are related to their chemical structure. Thus, characteristics such as the linkage
48 type, polymerization level (Wang et al., 2017) or degree of branching (Lehtovaara & Gu, 2011)
49 of such molecules might determine not only their biological but also their physic-chemical
50 properties (*e.g.* solubility) (Lehtovaara & Gu, 2011; Moreno et al., 2016; Thompson, Oyston, &
51 Williamson, 2010). Zhang, Li, Xu, & Zheng (2005) reported that the complexity of the helical
52 conformation (*i.e.* single or triple) determined the ability of the (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucans to
53 inhibit the tumour growth (Meng, Liang, & Luo, 2016). In addition, modified pachymaran, a
54 (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucan, also showed antitumor properties, after β -(1 \rightarrow 6) side chain removal
55 (Wang et al., 2017). These evidences indicated that preserving the structural integrity of fungal
56 β -D-glucans (mostly (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucans) during the extraction and analysis processes,
57 might be essential to maintain intact their bioactivities.

58 Protocols including hot water extractions are the most common methods to obtain fungal
59 polysaccharides (Ruthes et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2017). However, polysaccharides with complex
60 conformations require more aggressive extraction methods such as hot alkali solutions and the
61 use of chloroacetic or concentrated sulphuric acids, but they might also induce undesirable
62 structural modifications (Alzorqi, Singh, Manickam, & Al-Qrimli, 2017; Eskilsson & Bjorklund,

2000; Zhu, Du, & Xu, 2016). Alternatively, new extraction technologies using water such as pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) or microwave assisted extraction (MAE) were also studied as effective tools for harmless polysaccharide extractions (Smiderle et al., 2017). MAE uses microwaves energy to heat directly the extraction solvent without a heat transfer from the vessels to the solvent. It maintains thermal gradients to minima inducing a more homogeneous temperature through the sample (Eskilsson & Bjorklund, 2000). The high pressure generated during the extraction process maintains water in its liquid state at temperatures higher than its boiling point, accelerating mass transfer of compounds (Li, Dobruchowska, Gerwig, Dijkhuizen, & Kamerling, 2013; Ruthes et al., 2015). Several studies used MAE to extract total polysaccharides from mushrooms (Chen, Shao, Tao, & Wen, 2015; Wang & Li, 2010) however, only a few studied the β -D-glucans content of the obtained extracts (Ruthes et al., 2015; Zheng, Zhang, Gao, Jia, & Chen, 2012).

A common method used to study β -D-glucans is based on the sirofluor ability to bind polysaccharides with (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan branches (Alzorqi et al., 2017; Evans, Hoyne, & Stone, 1984; Ko & Lin, 2004). Some reports claimed that such fluorimetric method is selective for (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan binding but, it showed certain restrictions that were not always considered, for instance, the polymerization degree, presence/absence of substituents and their tridimensional conformation might modulate the fluorimetric determination (Evans et al., 1984; Ruthes et al., 2015).

Therefore, a three level factorial experimental design was carried out to find the most suitable MAE conditions to obtain β -D-glucans-enriched extracts using *Lentinula edodes* as mushroom model. Afterwards, a screening of other species was performed using similar extraction conditions. The influence of the (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan structure on the fluorimetric assay was studied (using also NMR) to remark its limitations and the method was adjusted to improve its accuracy for the detection of β -D-glucans in MAE extracts.

2. Experimental

2.1. Biological material, reagents and standard compounds

90 Powdered *Lentinula edodes* S. (Berkeley) fruiting bodies with a particle size lower than 0.5
91 mm and a moisture content less than 5% were purchased from Glucanfeed S.L. (La Rioja, Spain).
92 Dried fruiting bodies, commercially available in local markets, from *Auricularia judea* (Bull. Ex
93 St.Amans) Berck., *Cantharellus cibarius* (Fr.) *Cantharellus tubaeriformis* (Fr.), *Cantharellus*
94 *lutescens* (Hierve.) Fr., *Cantharellus cornucopoides* (L. Ex Fr.) Pers., *Boletus edulis* (Bull. Ex
95 Fr.), *Lactarius deliciosus* (Fr.), *Pleurotus pulmonarius* (Fr.) Quel., *Pleurotus eryngii* (D.C. Ex
96 Fr.) Quel, *Morchella conica* (Pers.), *Agrocybe aegerita* (Briganti) Singer, *Amanita caesarea*
97 (Scop. Ex Fri.) Pers. Ex Schw. and *Hypsizygus marmoreus* (Peck) H.E. Bigelow were purchased
98 and ground using a Grindomix GM200 Retsch mill (VERDER Group, The Netherlands) as
99 described by Ramirez-Anguiano, Santoyo, Reglero, & Soler-Rivas (2007). Powdered mushrooms
100 (MP) were stored at -20 °C under darkness until further use.

101 Absolute ethanol was purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) as well as concentrated
102 sulfuric acid. Phenol, sodium borohydride, sodium hydroxide pellets, glycine, aniline blue
103 diammonium salt 95% and hydrochloride acid 37% were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid,
104 Spain). Compounds used as standards were two linear β -D-glucans: curdlan (a (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan
105 from *Alcaligenes faecalis*, Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain) and a (1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucan isolated from
106 *A. bisporus* (named B6G) (Smiderle et al., 2013); and two branched (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucans:
107 schizophyllan from Contipro Biotech (Dolni Dobrouc, Czech Republic) and a chemically
108 characterized glucan (PUL, previously named B1316PP) extracted from *P. pulmonarius*
109 (Smiderle et al., 2008). Moreover, a heteropolysaccharide (mannogalactan, MG) isolated from *P.*
110 *pulmonarius* (Smiderle et al., 2008) and commonly found in Basidiomycetes, was also used to
111 compare with the β -D-glucans.

112 2.2. Microwave-assisted extractions (MAE)

113 Polysaccharides-enriched fractions (PEFs) were obtained using an automated microwave
114 extraction system coupled to a MAS 24 auto-sampler (Monowave 300, Anton Paar GmbH, Graz,
115 Austria). Extractions were performed at 1:30 mushroom powder:water ratio, 850W power, 2455
116 MHz frequency and 30 bar pressure as was described by Smiderle et al. (2017). After MAE, the
117 samples were centrifuged and the pellet discarded. An aliquot of the supernatant (200 μ L) was

118 used to estimate the total carbohydrate content (TCH) in the MAE extracts. Afterwards, the
 119 polysaccharides were precipitated with ethanol under cold conditions following the procedure of
 120 Smiderle et al. (2017). Obtained polysaccharide-enriched fractions (PEF) were collected, freeze-
 121 dried, weighted and kept at -20 °C until further use (equation 1, Figure 1).

122 (1) PEF yield (%) = $\frac{\text{weight of polysaccharide enriched fraction after MAE precipitation (g)}}{\text{weight of mushroom powder (g)}} \times 100$

123

124

Figure 1. Workflow of the experiments developed in this work. Superscripts 1-5 correspond to the specific equations used to determine the corresponding values.

125 2.3. Design of experiment (DoE) approach for MAE of *Lentinula edodes*

126 In order to explore the efficiency of MAE to obtain PEFs, a full factorial three level
 127 experimental design (3^k) was selected using *L. edodes* as mushroom model. Two factors (*k*),
 128 extraction temperature and time, were studied and their ranges were set according to the
 129 equipment limitations and results reported for other mushroom species (respectively 50 – 180 °C
 130 and 5 - 30 min) (Smiderle et al., 2017). PEF yield (% , g PEF/ 100 g MP) and TCH (mg equivalents

131 of glucose/ g MP) were selected as response variables. Eleven randomized extractions were
132 performed following the parameters indicated in Table 1, *i.e.* three levels per factor (3^2) with two
133 additional central points. Most convenient MAE conditions achieved for *L. edodes* were selected
134 to obtain PEFs from the other mushroom species.

135 2.4. Determination of carbohydrates from MAE extracts

136 The total carbohydrate content (TCH) in MAE extracts and PEFs (obtained after precipitation
137 of MAE extracts) (Figure 1) was measured using the phenol-sulfuric acid method, as detailed by
138 Smiderle et al. (2017). Since only traces of monosaccharides or oligosaccharides might remain in
139 obtained PEFs, in this case, the TCH values indicated the total polysaccharide (PSC)
140 concentration. Calculations were performed as follow (including unit conversions),

141 (2) TCH in MAE extracts (mg/g) = $\frac{\text{equivalents of glucose in MAE extracts (mg)}}{\text{weight of MP (g)}}$

142 (3) TCH (or total PSC) in PEFs (mg/g) = $\frac{\text{equivalents of glucose in PEF (mg)}}{\text{weight of PEF (g)}}$

143 (4) PSC in MP after MAE ppt. (%) = $\frac{\frac{\text{equivalents of glucose in PEF (mg)}}{\text{weight of PEF (g)}} \times \frac{\text{weight of PEF (g)}}{\text{weight of MP (g)}}}{10 \text{ (unit conversion)}}$

144 (5) Other sugars in MP after MAE ppt. (%) = $\frac{\text{TCH in MAE extracts}}{10 \text{ (unit conversion)}} - \text{PSC in MP by MAE precipitation}$

145 Supernatants obtained after MAE (equation 2, Figure 1) were diluted for all species as 1:15
146 (extract: water) except for *L. edodes* (1:5) and for *A. judea* and *P. eryngii* (1:30). TCH in PEFs
147 (equation 3, Figure 1) were diluted for all species as 1:5. Samples were analyzed in triplicate and
148 glucose was used as standard.

149 2.5. Determination of (1 → 3)-β-D-glucans from PEF

150 β-D-Glucans were determined by the fluorimetric method firstly described by Evans et al.
151 (1984). This method uses an impurity from the aniline blue stain (sirofluor) as fluorochrome
152 because of its ability to bind polysaccharides with (1 → 3)-β-linkages (Figure 1). Thus, the
153 presence of (1 → 3)-β-D-glucans was determined in freeze-dried MAE polysaccharide fractions
154 (PEF) using the method reported by Ko & Lin (2004) with some modifications concerning the
155 sample preparation and the analytical procedure. Briefly, fractions were solubilized in 0.05 M

156 NaOH with 1% NaBH₄ (0.02 mg/mL) to preserve the polysaccharides integrity. Then, samples
157 (300 μL) were mixed with 30 μL of 6 M NaOH and 630 μL of a dye solution (0.1% aniline: 1 M
158 HCl: 1 M glycine/NaOH buffer pH 9.5 33:18:49, v/v/v) and incubated at 50 °C for 30 min in a
159 water bath. Each mixture (250 μL) was transferred to a 96-well plate and analyzed using a M200
160 Plate Reader (Tecan, Mannedorf, Switzerland) with excitation and emission wavelengths of 398
161 nm and 502 nm respectively. The buffer was freshly prepared before use to avoid degradation.

162 Fluorescence signals relative to the β-D-glucans content in PEF were obtained at 0.002, 0.01
163 and 0.02 mg/mL for all previously mentioned species. The standards for β-D-glucans were used
164 in a range of 0-0.02 mg/mL for calibration curves and a solution of 0.05 M NaOH with 1% NaBH₄
165 was used as blank. Determinations were carried out in triplicate. The selection of the adequate
166 standard for the detection of (1 → 3)-β-D-glucans in a mushroom extract was dependent on
167 recorded fluorescence slopes.

168 2.6. Analysis of monosaccharide composition by GC-MS

169 The polysaccharide-enriched fractions (PEF) from MAE extracts (1 mg) were hydrolyzed
170 with 2 M TFA at 100 °C for 8 h, followed by evaporation to dryness (Figure 1). The dried
171 carbohydrate samples were dissolved in distilled water (100 μL) and 1 mg NaBH₄ was added.
172 The solution was held at room temperature overnight to reduce aldoses into alditols (Sasaki et
173 al., 2008). The product was dried, the excess of NaBH₄ neutralized by the addition of acetic acid
174 and removed with methanol (x 2) under a compressed air stream. Alditols acetylation was
175 performed in pyridine–Ac₂O (200 μL; 1:1, v/v), for 30 min at 100 °C. The pyridine was removed
176 by washing with 5% CuSO₄ solution and the resulting alditol acetates were extracted with CHCl₃.
177 The resulting derivatives were analyzed by GC-MS (Varian CP-3800 gas chromatograph coupled
178 to an Ion-Trap 4000 mass spectrometer), using a VF5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d.) programmed
179 from 100 to 280 °C at 10 °C/min, with He as carrier gas. The obtained monosaccharides were
180 identified by their typical retention time compared to commercially available standards. Results
181 were expressed as mol%, calculated according to Pettolino, Walsh, Fincher, & Bacic (2012).

182 2.7. Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

183 NMR spectra (HSQC and HSQC-DEPT) from PEFs (Figure 1) were obtained using a 400
184 MHz Bruker model Avance III spectrometer with a 5 mm inverse probe. The analyses were
185 performed at 70 °C and the samples (30 mg) were dissolved in D₂O (400 µL). Chemical shifts are
186 expressed in ppm (δ) relative to resonance of acetone at δ 30.2 and 2.22 corresponding to ¹³C and
187 ¹H signals, respectively. NMR signals were assigned on the basis of 2D NMR experiment (HSQC)
188 and literature data.

189 2.8. Statistical analysis

190 In order to set the experimental conditions and detect the optimal MAE parameters, analysis
191 of variance (two-way ANOVA test) was carried out using the Statgraphics Centurion XVI
192 software (Statpoint Technologies, Warrenton, Virginia, USA). The confidence level was set at
193 95% (p < 0.05) for all cases.

194 3. Results and discussion

195 3.1. Response surface study of microwave assisted extractions from *L. edodes*.

196 Powdered fruiting bodies from *Lentinula edodes* were submitted to MAE following a full
197 factorial 3² experimental design. Two factors, extraction time and temperature, were tested to
198 estimate the more convenient combination to obtain high TCH values and PEF yields (Table 1).

Table 1. Full factorial 3² experimental design for *L. edodes* MAE. ¹TCH, total carbohydrates content in MAE extracts; ²mg equiv. Glc/g MP, milligrams of equivalent glucose per gram of mushroom powder. ³ PEF yield, polysaccharide yield of the enriched fraction (PEF) obtained from MAE extracts.

Exp. Number	Factors		Response variables	
	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	TCH in MAE ¹ extracts (mg equiv. Glc/g MP) ²	PEF yield ³ % (w/w)
1	180	5	263.21 ± 18.4	15
2	50	5	107.52 ± 5.8	4.6
3	115	30	88.62 ± 3.12	4.4
4	50	17.5	107.36 ± 8.5	4
5	115	17.5	83.33 ± 2.0	4
6	115	5	98.65 ± 31.0	5
7	115	17.5	86.21 ± 31.4	3.4
8	50	30	116.80 ± 4.9	2.8
9	180	30	290.43 ± 20.6	15.4
10	180	17.5	238.76 ± 12.5	16.4
11	115	17.5	80.38 ± 19.2	3.6

199 Similar trends in the response surface plots for both variables were obtained (Figure 2),
200 higher TCH and yields were reached at the highest tested temperatures. The model showed an
201 adequate fitting to experimental data supported by the elevated variability percentage in TCH and
202 yield explained by the model (99.4 and 98.8% respectively). The regression equations fitting to
203 the data were:

$$204 \quad y_1 = 13.1 - 0.22x_1 - 0.12x_2 + 1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}x_1^2 + 6.7 \cdot 10^{-4}x_1x_2 + 6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}x_2^2$$

$$205 \quad y_2 = 281.08 - 4.12x_1 - 3.89x_2 + 0.02x_1^2 + 5.5 \cdot 10^{-3}x_1x_2 + 0.1x_2^2$$

206 where the linear and quadratic effects of both factors (x_1 = temperature and x_2 = time) as well as
207 the interaction between them were included for y_1 (yield) and y_2 (TCH) prediction. Only ‘linear’
208 and ‘temperature’ quadratic terms showed a statistically significant influence on the TCH and
209 yield, following the analysis of the variance results (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$). The factor ‘time’ as well
210 as the interaction between both factors, were defined as statistically insignificant. However,
211 according to the Pareto charts for each variable response (Supplementary Figure 1), the term
212 ‘quadratic time’ affected more to TCH content than to the yield. This effect can be easily
213 visualized in the respective response surface plotting by the curvature along time (Figure 2a).

Figure 2. Estimated response surfaces plots for a) TCH content and b) PEF yields after MAE from *L. edodes*.

214 The temperature and time values that maximize the TCH and PEF yields of MAEs, within
 215 the selected conditions ranges, were 180 °C and 30 min. These values were similar to those
 216 previously described for other mushroom species such as *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Ganoderma*
 217 *lucidum* after a similar extraction procedure (Smiderle et al., 2017). The desirable linear
 218 regression obtained by the plot observed vs. predicted values for each variable response validated
 219 the model (Supplementary Figure 2). Nevertheless, to verify it, three additional microwave-
 220 assisted extractions from *L. edodes* were performed at 180 °C and 30 min. Only slightly lower
 221 values were observed for TCH (224.4 ± 6.1 mg equiv. Glc/g MP) and higher values for PEF yield
 222 ($19.1 \pm 0.3\%$, w/w) were noticed compared to the software predicted values (respectively 278 mg
 223 equiv. Glc/g and 15% w/w). Therefore, the predictive model fitted the experimental behavior.

224 Substantially higher PEF yields were observed after MAE compared to the recoveries
225 previously reported for conventional hot water extractions, *i.e.* 5.3% were obtained after seven
226 extractions at 100 °C for 200 min (Zhu, Nie, Liang, & Wang, 2013). The higher MAE efficiency
227 could be explained by the more effective disruption of analytes-matrix interactions and an
228 improved mass transference at high temperatures and pressures, resulting in larger recoveries
229 (Plaza & Turner, 2015). However, their higher solubilization might also indicate that MAE could
230 generate some physical changes in the tertiary conformations of the polysaccharides enhancing
231 their extractability (Wang et al., 2017) and/or that some chemical changes such as partial
232 hydrolysis might occur as indicated by other studies (Synytsya et al., 2014; Ookushi, Sakamoto,
233 & Azuma, 2006). Nevertheless, since the extraction yield steadily increased and no drastic
234 changes were observed/predicted at least up to 180 °C, the latter possibility seemed unlikely.

235 3.2. Microwave-assisted extractions from other edible mushrooms

236 MAE were also carried out at 180 °C and during 30 min for the other selected species since
237 with these parameters, the highest TCH and PEF yields were obtained for *L. edodes* and,
238 according to Smiderle et al. (2017), they were also appropriate for other two mushrooms. The
239 yields of obtained PEFs from the selected species ranged between 12.1 (*Cantharellus cibarius*)
240 and 19.1 % (*L. edodes*) except for *Auricularia judea* that showed extremely high yields (Table
241 2). However, the MAE extracts that showed higher TCH values besides *Auricularia judea* were
242 *Pleurotus eryngii*, *Lentinula edodes* and *Boletus edulis* indicating that the latter two species
243 contain higher levels of monosaccharides and oligosaccharides than the rest of species. In the case
244 of *A. judea*, results indicated that almost half of the dry matter from the mushroom powder could
245 be extracted using MAE obtaining PEFs with 96.4% polysaccharides. *L. edodes* yields were in
246 the range of the previously observed values (15.4%) as also noticed for the other species *i.e.*
247 *Armillaria luteovirens* (8.40 - 8.34%) (Chen et al., 2015), *G. lucidum* (11.2%) (Smiderle et al.,
248 2017), *Fomitopsis ulmaria* (8.36%) (Zhao, Tang, Liu, & Zhang, 2014) etc. Other mushrooms
249 such as *Morchella conica* showed PEF yields (16.5%) slightly higher than other MAE obtained
250 extracts previously reported (5.86%) (Xu et al., 2018) and *Pleurotus pulmonarius* showed lower

251 values than other related species such as *P. ostreatus* (32.4%) (Smiderle et al., 2017). However,
252 the different extraction conditions such as shorter times and/or different mushroom varieties or
253 cultivation conditions, might be the reason for the noticed differences.

254 The TCH content determined in PEFs indicated their polysaccharides concentration (since
255 only traces of monosaccharides or oligosaccharides might be present after the precipitation
256 procedure). Results indicated that, indeed, PEFs were fractions with high polysaccharide content
257 except for *Craterellus cornucopioides* (40.3%). PEF obtained from mushrooms such as *Amanita*
258 *caesarea*, *Agrocybe aegerita* or *Hypsizygus marmoreus* contained 63.6 to 68.2% PSCs. The rest
259 of the PEF weight might be proteins (perhaps bound to polysaccharides as glucoproteins or
260 proteoglycans) as some of them might also precipitate with the ethanol concentrations utilized.

261 For certain fungal species, MAE seems to be a more efficient method to obtain
262 polysaccharides than conventional methods or other advanced techniques but not for all.
263 Pressurized water extractions (PWE) extracted higher polysaccharide amounts than MAE from
264 *P. ostreatus* but not significant differences were noticed when the polysaccharides were extracted
265 from *G. lucidum* (Smiderle et al., 2017). Moreover, *L. edodes* showed a 21% PSCs extraction
266 yield using PWE at higher temperatures (200 °C and 10.7 MPa) but 4.71% was recovered when
267 extraction was carried out at 150 °C (Zhu et al., 2013), values very similar to MAE where a 19.1%
268 yield was noticed. Ultrasound-assisted extractions (UAE) were also tested using several
269 mushrooms however, they were usually less effective than MAE, for instance UAE from the latter
270 mushroom extracted 9.75% PSCs, meaning 1.6 fold increase compared to conventional hot water
271 extraction but still lower than observed using MAE (Zhao, Yang, Liu, Zhao, & Wang, 2018).

Table 2. Total carbohydrate contents (TCH) in MAE extracts (mg/g), yields of obtained polysaccharide-enriched fraction (PEF) after MAE precipitation, TCH (mg/g) in PEF, PSC (%) in PEF and PSC (%), as well as other sugars, after MAE precipitation. *n=3 independent colorimetric measurements for TCH determination, † n=2 independent MAE extractions.

Species	TCH in MAE extracts (mg/g)*	PEF yield % (w/w)†	TCH in PEF (mg/g)*	PSC in PEFs (%)	PSC in MP after MAE precipitation (%)	Other sugars in MP after MAE precipitation (%)
<i>A. judea</i>	485.5 ± 11.0	44.2 ± 1.3	964.6 ± 65.5	96.4	42.64	5.91
<i>A. aegerita</i>	175 ± 3.9	17.6 ± 0.3	682.7 ± 42.5	68.2	12.02	5.48
<i>A. caesaria</i>	180.6 ± 5.5	13.9 ± 1.2	636.4 ± 37.2	63.3	8.85	9.21
<i>B. edulis</i>	226.9 ± 12.8	12.3 ± 0.1	588.8 ± 8.8	58.8	7.24	15.45
<i>C. cibarius</i>	140.3 ± 31	12.1 ± 0.3	567.5 ± 49.6	56.7	6.87	7.16
<i>C. cornucopioides</i>	87.19 ± 7.9	15.3 ± 0.6	403.4 ± 1.7	40.3	6.17	2.55
<i>C. lutescens</i>	157.4 ± 18.9	15.7 ± 0.1	608.8 ± 40.7	60.8	9.56	6.18
<i>C. tubaeformis</i>	91.3 ± 3.4	16.4 ± 0.1	511.1 ± 34.8	51.1	8.38	0.75
<i>H. marmoreus</i>	184.8 ± 1.0	12.8 ± 1.4	681.5 ± 79.2	68.1	8.72	9.76
<i>L. deliciosus</i>	140.8 ± 11.0	17.8 ± 0.1	561.2 ± 26.5	56.1	9.99	4.09
<i>L. edodes</i>	290.43 ± 20.6	15.4 ± 0.4	563.7 ± 33.6	56.3	8.68	20.32
<i>M. conica</i>	143.4 ± 3.5	16.5 ± 0.9	552.4 ± 53.1	55.2	9.11	5.23
<i>P. eryngii</i>	301.2 ± 16.0	16.8 ± 0.2	593.8 ± 30.1	59.3	9.98	20.14
<i>P. pulmonarius</i>	166.6 ± 3.1	15.4 ± 0.3	585 ± 10.6	58.5	9.01	7.65

272 3.3. Adjustments of the fluorimetric method for fungal (1→3)-β-D-glucans determination

273 The fluorimetric method is based on the sirofluor preference for binding to (1→3)-β-D-
274 glucans. Although an increased signal emission intensity can be expected with higher number of
275 these branches, there is not a direct correlation since the fluorescence intensity is affected by the
276 polysaccharide structure (Evans et al., 1984). Ko & Lin (2004) also indicated the influence of the
277 structure and conformation of (1→3)-β-D-glucans to the fluorescence profiles of nine standards,
278 e.g. pachymanan, yeast glucans, curdlan. Therefore, the maintenance of the β-D-glucan native
279 structure during their extraction process is critical for a reliable identification and quantification.
280 However, in previous studies, insufficient attention was given to sample preparation to keep the
281 integrity of these molecules, usually a conventional protocol was followed (Ko & Lin, 2004).
282 Thus, the fluorimetric method used to determine fungal (1→3)-β-D-glucans was adapted at
283 several stages, from the sample preparation to the selection of the adequate standard compound
284 for the β-D-glucan quantification.

285 The PEFs obtained with MAE were not completely soluble in water at room temperature
286 but in alkalis. However, a careful post-extraction treatment of the samples should be carried out,
287 avoiding drastic changes that could compromise the chemical integrity of the β -D-glucans.
288 Treatment with sodium hydroxide improve β -D-glucans separation from impurities and facilitate
289 their quantification but could modify their helical 3-D conformations (Lehtovaara & Gu, 2011;
290 Young, Dong, & Jacobs, 2000) and in high concentrations could damage even the primary
291 structure. Therefore, a solution of 0.05 M instead 1 M NaOH (Ko & Lin, 2004) was used to
292 dissolve β -D-glucans since the lower concentration was able to dissolve the samples and
293 standards. NaBH₄ (1% w/v) was also added to the NaOH solution to protect the polysaccharide
294 chains from degradation (Whistler & BeMiller, 1958). Indeed, addition of NaBH₄ enhanced 17
295 % the fluorescence intensity of curdlan compared to a similar solution without the reducing agent.
296 Moreover, previous studies remarked the importance of the incubation step at 80 °C for 30 min
297 to enhance the complex between sirofluor and the polysaccharides with (1→3)- β -D-
298 glucopyranose-linkages (Ko & Lin, 2004). However, if lower temperatures were tested (down to
299 50°C), no differences in fluorescence intensity were noticed therefore, fifty degrees were selected
300 to protect the polysaccharides from thermic de-polymerization.

301 Isolated polysaccharides including the β -D-glucans-linkages frequently described in
302 mushrooms were selected as representative standards to adjust the fluorimetric method. When
303 these β -D-glucans were treated according to the modified method, linear (1→3)- β -D-glucans such
304 as curdlan emitted intense fluorescence, but moderate fluorescence was noticed for branched
305 (1→3)-(1→6)- β -D-glucans (Figure 3a). Schizophyllan and PUL were both (1→3)- β -D-glucans
306 with (1→6)- β -D-Glc unit branching respectively every 3 and 2.7 residues of the backbone chain
307 (Zhang, Kong, Fang, Nishinari, & Philips, 2013; Smiderle et al., 2008) and therefore, they showed
308 slight differences in their degree of branching (DB) (0.33 for schizophyllan and 0.37 for PUL).
309 Moreover, when β -glucans from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were analyzed (DB = 0.03-0.2)
310 (Synytsya & Novak, 2013), an intermediate fluorescence was noticed between curdlan (DB = 0)
311 and schizophyllan suggesting that higher DB might fold the molecules more compact or tighter,
312 impairing the binding of the fluorophore to the (1→3)-linkages of the backbone chain. This effect

313 might result in a fluorescence reduction and indeed, PUL showed a slightly lower fluorescence
314 intensity than schizophyllan. Computer modeling studies using glucans with different
315 configurations (α or β) and linkages, suggested that (1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucans might show highly
316 flexible 3D conformation due to an easy rotation freedom between glucose residues, while (1 \rightarrow 3)-
317 β -D-glucans showed helical and flexible conformations (including also glucans with O-6-
318 branches) (Zhang, Cui, Cheung, & Wang, 2007). These observations indicated that the helical
319 conformation was essential for the sirofluor fluorescence stimulation. Thus, a linear (1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-
320 glucan (B6G) and a mannogalactan (MG) were also tested under the adjusted conditions and both
321 lacked fluorescence. This result confirmed that still after the protocol modifications, sirofluor was
322 binding to β -D-glucans with helical conformations including linear or/and branched (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-
323 glucans.

324 Since each mushroom species synthesizes its own particular set of β -D-glucans, a wide
325 variety of primary structures, degrees of branching and conformations are described (Synytsya &
326 Novak, 2013). When the PEF obtained by MAE from several selected species were analyzed to
327 detect the fluorescence of their β -D-glucans, a range of responses was noticed (Figure 3b), leading
328 to slightly similar slope values. The lowest and highest data were respectively for *M. conica* and
329 *A. caesarea* (Table 3) showing fluorescence values closer to PUL than to schizophyllan or
330 curdlan. Obviously, the extracts contained many β -D-glucans showing several structures and
331 conformations that were all contributing to the fluorescence intensity while signals from curdlan
332 and schizophyllan are exclusive. However, only curdlan (linear (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan) is frequently
333 used as standard for the β -D-glucan quantification regardless the mushroom source and most of
334 the edible species (basidiomycetes) contain larger amounts of branched (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-
335 glucans than (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucan (more common in ascomycetes) (Ruthes et al., 2015). Thus, by
336 using curdlan as standard, the β -D-glucan concentration of many mushroom species might be
337 underestimated or misunderstood. For instance, the β -D-glucan content for *A. aegerita* PEF were
338 140.1 mg/g using curdlan and 522.3 mg/g using a (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucan (PUL) as standards
339 (Table 3). For most of the tested species, results obtained using curdlan or PUL were significantly
340 different (one-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$)) (Table 3). Thus, since the major compounds in

341 basidiomycetes are branched (1→3),(1→6)-β-D-glucans, it should be expected a higher
 342 contribution of these structures to the total polysaccharide fractions than linear glucans.
 343 Therefore, PUL might be a more suitable compound to be used as standard than curdlan, even
 344 schizophyllan could also be adequate and more convenient since it is commercially available and
 345 would induce a lower quantification error than curdlan (Figure 3b).

Figure 3. Fluorescence intensity of a) standard β-D-glucans and a mannogalactan (MG) b) the PEFs extracted by MAE from several mushroom species. The regression equation for the standards are included.

346 For the same reason, depending on whether PUL or curdlan are used as standard (Table 3),
 347 the PEFs composition might be completely different. For instance, the (1→3)-β-D-glucans

348 represented 14.8% of the polysaccharides from *A. judea* PEF when curdlan is used as standards
349 while using PUL, 63.2% of the PEF polysaccharides were (1→3)-β-D-glucans. Similarly, the β-
350 glucan percentages found in PEFs seemed to be highly underestimated in other species such as *A.*
351 *agerita*, *H. marmoreus*, *M. conica* etc. These results could be supported by those previously
352 reported by Synytsya & Novak (2013) and Smiderle et al. (2011, 2017) where β-D-glucans were
353 found in higher concentrations than other polysaccharides such as α-glucans, chitins,
354 heteropolysaccharides etc. If β-D-glucans are quantified using curdlan their contribution to the
355 total polysaccharide values is quite low to be the predominant compound within the
356 polysaccharide fractions.

357 However, quantification using PUL could also overestimate their contribution to the
358 polysaccharides content because in the case of species such as *A. caesarea*, *P. eryngii* and *B.*
359 *edulis* the estimation of β-D-glucans was almost 2-fold the amount of total polysaccharides.
360 Nevertheless, the phenol-sulfuric acid method estimates the PSC concentration mainly because
361 glucose residues are generated with the digestion, if other monosaccharides (xylose, mannose,
362 galactose, etc.) are generated, the method precision decreases. These results bring a suspicious
363 about the suitability of the fluorimetric method for the quantification of β-D-glucans in a complex
364 polysaccharide matrix.

365 On the other hand, the fluorimetric determinations (independently of the utilized standard)
366 indicated that the polysaccharides detected in PEFs obtained from mushrooms belonging to the
367 Cantharellales order (*Cantharellus lutescens*, *Cantharellus cibarius*, *C. cornucopioides* and
368 *C. tubaeformis*) (Table 2) might be different than (1→3)-β-D-glucans, or contain also other
369 polysaccharides interfering in the sirofluor complexation, as no fluorescence was detected (Table
370 3).

Table 3. Fluorescence (emission at 503 nm) of PEFs extracted by MAE from several edible mushrooms and their (1→3)-β-D-glucans concentration depending on the standard utilized (curdlan or PUL). n=2 MAE extracts per species; n=2 fluorimetric measurements per PEF; n.d. no signal detected. The linear fitting of the curves (R^2) was 0.99 for all the mushroom species. *

Data statistically different (one-way ANOVA, $p > 0.05$, 95% confidence level) between standards for the same species.

Species	Fluorescence results (AU)				(1→3)-β-D-glucans (mg/g) in PEFs		(1→3)-β-D-glucans of PSC (%)	
	0.002 mg/mL	0.01 mg/mL	0.02 mg/mL	Curve slope	Curdlan	PUL	Curdlan	PUL
<i>A. judea</i>	30.25 ± 11.5	159.5 ± 56.6	295 ± 86.3	14829	142.7 ± 49.3	610.0 ± 234.1	14.8	63.2
<i>A. aegerita</i>	18.7 ± 6.6	135.7 ± 11.1	298.2 ± 15.3	14637	140.15 ± 8.62*	522.6 ± 37.0*	20.5	76.5
<i>A. caesarea</i>	37 ± 7.7	231 ± 43.3	481.5 ± 78.0	24266	245.94 ± 43.1*	1249.9 ± 241.6*	38.6	196.4
<i>B. edulis</i>	37.7 ± 10.6	207.5 ± 55.0	446.2 ± 110.6	22401	229.21 ± 63.2	1020.3 ± 300.1	38.9	173.3
<i>C. cibarius</i>	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	-	-
<i>C. cornucopioides</i>	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	-	-
<i>C. lutescens</i>	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		2.12 ± 2.12	n.d.	0.3	-
<i>C. tubaeformis</i>	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.		n.d.	n.d.	-	-
<i>H. marmoreus</i>	17.2 ± 4.3	115 ± 10.0	250.7 ± 33.0	12643	120.0 ± 18.5*	543.6 ± 13.8*	17.6	79.8
<i>L. deliciosus</i>	22.7 ± 5.3	178 ± 19.6	368.5 ± 22.1	18716	184.7 ± 12.4*	713.7 ± 53.5*	32.9	127.2
<i>L. edodes</i>	23.5 ± 12.0	135 ± 0	311.5 ± 10.6	15593	152.7 ± 5.9*	647.1 ± 28.7*	27.1	114.8
<i>M. conica</i>	15.2 ± 5.7	102 ± 23.6	204 ± 42.3	10325	94.5 ± 23.1	400.5 ± 129.5	17.1	72.5
<i>P. eryngii</i>	32 ± 4.9	192.7 ± 18.0	445 ± 37.1	22349	226.4 ± 20.3*	1140.5 ± 113.8*	38.1	192.1
<i>P. pulmonarius</i>	18.7 ± 4.8	156.7 ± 14.4	337.7 ± 36.2	17153	167.2 ± 20.3*	639.4 ± 87.5*	28.6	109.3

371 3.4. Chemical characterization of the PEFs extracted by MAE

372 In order to study the real β-D-glucans contribution to the fluorescence intensity noticed (and
373 to the total polysaccharide values of the PEFs) as well as the method quantification accuracy, the
374 monosaccharide composition and structure of PEFs were monitored.

375 The PEFs that exhibited fluorescence contained more than 64% glucose in their
376 monosaccharide composition (Table 4). Species that did not show fluorescence, belonging to the
377 genus *Cantharellus*, showed lower glucose content (51.4 - 42.9%) but considerable amounts of
378 mannose (29.1 – 38 %) and xylose comparing to the other species. The mushroom from the
379 Boletales order (*B. edulis*) showed higher galactose levels than the rest of selected species. Fucose
380 monosaccharide was only found in few species at levels below 3%. Moreover, methyl-hexose
381 was detected in Pleurotaceae mushrooms (*P. eryngii* and *P. pulmonarius*) and in *B. edulis* in low

382 amounts. Therefore, the slight differences observed in the monosaccharide composition are not
 383 consistent enough to explain the different slopes noticed in the fluorescence regression equations.
 384 For example, *P.eryngii* and *H.marmoreus* showed similar monosaccharide composition (~82%
 385 glucose, ~5% galactose and ~10% mannose) however, the regression slope of the first one was
 386 1.8 fold the other, suggesting that sugar moieties might not be highly involved in the fluorescence
 387 observed (Tables 3 and 4). Wise to take into consideration was the fact that those mushrooms
 388 showing high β -glucan contents (even higher than their PSC values) *i.e.* *A. caesarea* or *P. eryngii*
 389 also showed high glucose contents (above 80%). The PSC levels of the Chantarelle family might
 390 also be underestimated because they contained large amounts of other monosaccharides that are
 391 not glucoses (*i.e.* *C. lutescens* contains 38% mannose and 13.7 % xylose) adding larger errors to
 392 the colorimetric determination.

Table 4. Monosaccharide composition (%) of PEFs obtained by MAE. ^a % of peak area relative to total peak areas, determined by GC–MS; ^b Trace amounts \leq 0.5%.

Species	Monosaccharides (%) ^a					
	Fucose	Xylose	Methyl-Hexose	Mannose	Galactose	Glucose
<i>A. judea</i>	-	3.4	-	14.3	-	82.3
<i>A. aegerita</i>	2.3	-	-	3.6	5.3	88.8
<i>A. caesarea</i>	1.8	-	-	5.8	5.2	87.2
<i>B. edulis</i>	Tr. ^b	2.3	Tr. ^b	22.8	10.1	64.2
<i>C. cibarius</i>	Tr. ^b	12.7	-	35.9	-	51.2
<i>C. cornucopioides</i>	Tr. ^b	15.8	-	33.5	5.9	44.5
<i>C. lutescens</i>	Tr. ^b	13.7	-	38.0	5.3	42.7
<i>C. tubaeformis</i>	Tr. ^b	21.8	-	29.1	4.7	44.1
<i>H. marmoreus</i>	Tr. ^b	1.8	-	9.9	5.5	82.7
<i>L. deliciosus</i>	Tr. ^b	3.1	-	12.0	6.5	78.2
<i>L. edodes</i>	1.6	2.1	-	14.3	4.9	77.0
<i>M. conica</i>	-	-	-	10.3	4.0	85.7
<i>P. eryngii</i>	-	-	2.5	10.8	4.9	81.8
<i>P. pulmonarius</i>	Tr. ^b	1.3	2.6	8.9	6.8	79.8

393 Signals observed in the HSQC spectra from PEFs were in concordance with the
394 monosaccharides determined for each species. The most representative spectra are compiled in
395 Figure 4, while the others are supplied as supplementary material (Supplementary Figure 3). With
396 exception of *M. conica*, spectra from *A. caesarea*, *C. lutescens*, *L. edodes* (Figure 4a, b and c), *A.*
397 *aegerita* or *B. edulis* (Supplementary Figure 3), showed intense signals at δ 102.8/4.52 and
398 102.8/4.72 relative to C-1 of β -D-Glcp; at δ 85.0/3.75 relative to C-3 *O*-substituted and; at δ
399 69.0/4.19 and 69.0/3.86 relative to CH₂ *O*-substituted of the same units. These data suggest the
400 presence of β -D-glucans (1 \rightarrow 3)-(1 \rightarrow 6)-linked (de Jesus et al., 2017). The O-6 substitution was
401 confirmed by inversion of CH₂ signals of DEPT-HSQC experiment (data not shown). Linear
402 (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucans signals could be overlapped to the branched β -D-glucans, therefore a
403 separation process might be required to quantify each of them. Besides, signals at δ 99.8/5.36 and
404 δ 77.7/3.64 were intense in *L. edodes* (Figure 4c) and *M. conica* (Figure 4d) spectra, characteristic
405 of C-1 of α -D-Glcp and C-4 *O*-substituted, indicating the presence of glycogen (α -1,4-1,6-D-
406 glucan), the energy stock of fungi (Synystya & Novak, 2013). Small intensity signals of α -D-
407 Galp were observed in all spectra at δ 98.0/4.98 and signals of β -D-Manp were observed mainly
408 in *C. lutescens*, *B. edulis*, and *L. edodes* at δ ~101.6/5.14-102.3/5.11. Species from genus
409 *Cantharellus* showed the higher xylose content, that is not commonly observed in mushrooms
410 and its presence was confirmed by signals at δ ~103.6/4.42 in the spectra of all *Cantharellus*
411 species (Figure 4b and Supplementary Figure 3). Mannogalactans, fucomannogalactans and
412 xylomannans were already isolated from other basidiomycetes such as *P. pulmonarius*, *Amanita*
413 *muscaria*, and *Flammulina velutipes* (Smiderle et al., 2008; Ruthes et al., 2013; Smiderle et al.,
414 2006), which confirms the findings in this study. Considering that β -D-glucans are able to
415 complex with sirofluor and *Cantharellus* species did not show fluorescence, it is possible that
416 polysaccharides containing xylose and mannose (present in high amounts in these species) may
417 influence the β -D-glucans 3D conformation present in *Cantharellus* PEFs. These types of
418 polysaccharides were also previously pointed as indirect scavengers of smaller molecules because

419 of their gelling properties so, they could partially attach to sirofluor provoking a lower
420 fluorescence emission (Ngwuluka, Ocheke, & Aruoma, 2016). Furthermore, *M. conica* showed
421 low fluorescence and its HSQC spectrum presented more intense glycogen signals than signals
422 of β -D-glucans in comparison to the other species, indicating that glycogen might also interfere
423 the proper binding of the fluorochrome to the β -D-glucans structures.

424 Hence, the fluorimetric method seemed to be sensitive enough for the detection of small
425 amounts of (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucans in polysaccharide mixtures such a MAE extracts, with limits of
426 detection bellow 2 μ g/mL. So, it might be used as a fast and easy alternative to determine the
427 presence/absence of (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucans in complex mixtures, being tentatively applicable to
428 other biological sources. However, to be sure that these linkages are not present in the analyzed
429 samples when lack of fluorescence is observed, more exhaustive qualitative techniques (i.e.
430 NMR) must be performed. No specific correlation was obtained between the fluorescence
431 intensity noticed in the PEFs and their chemical composition suggesting that the fluorescence test
432 should not be recommended for an accurate and trustable quantification of the (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-glucans
433 content for any mushroom species. The presence of α -glucans and other polysaccharides, their
434 particular interactions and possible complexing between them or the sirofluor, might
435 under/overestimate their real concentrations depending on the species and standard considered.

Figure 4. HSQC NMR spectra of a) *Amanita caesarea*, b) *Cantharellus lutescens*, c) *Lentinula edodes* and d) *Morchella conica*. Experiments were performed in D₂O at 70 °C (chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm).

436 **4. Concluding remarks**

437 Microwave-assisted extraction is a friendly environmental technology that could be used to
 438 obtain polysaccharide-enriched fractions from edible mushrooms. The most suitable extraction
 439 conditions seemed to be applicable to many different species obtaining interesting β -D-glucan
 440 yields. Although the fluorimetric method resulted appropriate for β -D-glucan detection, this
 441 technique must not be used for quantification analysis and a few details should be taken into
 442 consideration when carrying it out. For instance, modifications such as reduction of the alkali
 443 concentration utilized for experiments, decrease of the incubation temperature and addition of
 444 NaBH₄ improved the polysaccharide stability. Utilization of branched (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucans
 445 (particularly PUL or the commercially available schizophyllan) instead of linear (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-
 446 glucans such as curdlan lowered the experimental error because the fluorescence intensity was
 447 influenced by the degree of branching (DB) of the β -D-glucans and most of the mushrooms
 448 showed (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)-branched structures in high levels. Moreover, in the case that no

449 fluorescence is observed using the aniline-blue method for mushroom extracts a more exhaustive
450 analysis (i.e. NMR) must be carried out before discarding the sample to avoid misinterpretations
451 (as noticed in the *Cantharellus* genus). Perhaps the presence of other polysaccharides and/or their
452 particular tridimensional configurations negatively affected the preference of fluorophore to bind
453 (1→3),(1→6)-β-D-glucans. Deeper studies on the tridimensional folding possibilities of
454 (1→3),(1→6)-β-D-glucans and their complexing with other polysaccharides are required to
455 clarify this artefact before using the method for these mushroom species.

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Supplementary information

a)

b)

Supplementary Figure 1. Predicted effect of factors 'temperature' and 'time' and their interactions on a) TCH content and b) the PEF yield, sorted in decreasing order of importance. Red line represents $p=0.05$.

a)

b)

Supplementary Figure 2. Observed vs. predicted values of a) TCH content and b) PEFs yield from *L. edodes* after MAE. Dashed lines correspond to the perfect fit line (y-intercept=0, slope=1).

Supplementary Figure 3. HSQC NMR spectra of a) *Auricularia judea*, b) *Agrocybe aegerita*, c) *Boletus edulis*, d) *Cantharellus cibarius*, e) *Cantharellus cornucopioides*, f) *Cantharellus tubaeformis*, g) *Hypsizygus marmoreus*, h) *Lactarius deliciosus*, i) *Pleurotus eryngii* and j) *Pleurotus pulmonarius*. Experiments were performed in D₂O at 70 °C (chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm).